

Studies on the Bacterial Decomposition of Humic Acid in the Clay-humus Mixtures

B. C. Sen

Stabilisation of humus by its possible interaction with the clay minerals has been sought from a study of the bacterial decomposition of humus alone and in combination with clays. The rate of bacterial decomposition of humic acid has been found to be decreased when it is mixed with clay minerals with or without the presence of the metal ions. The humic acid has thus been stabilised by combining with the negative clay micelles through H^+ or metal ion bonding, the latter being stronger than the former.

Due to the complex nature of humus, its interaction with clays cannot be conveniently studied by means of ordinary chemical methods. Some physico-chemical methods, viz., studies on base-exchange capacity, adsorption, and viscosity, were used for this purpose, the detailed results of which have been given in the previous communications (*Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 23, 145, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 793). Since humic acid is also amenable to biological methods for its estimation, this line of investigation is likely to hold promise. From the investigation of Ensminger and Giesekeing (*Soil Sci.*, 1942, 53, 205) and Erickson (Ph.D. thesis, University of Illinois, 1948), it has been found that the decay characteristics of some organic materials are often quite different in free as compared to that adsorbed by clay minerals. The increased resistivity of humus, when adsorbed by the clay minerals, to biological decomposition was first observed by Waksman ("Humus: Origin, Chemical Composition, and Importance in Nature") because of the fact that the humus content in a clay-rich soil can be more easily built than in a clay-poor soil. An answer as to whether this is so because of the stabilisation of humus by its possible interaction with the clay, has been sought from a study of the bacterial decomposition of humus alone and in combination with clays. Conversely, the resistance to bacterial decomposition has been used to furnish a measure of the extent of clay-humus interaction. In the present work the rate of bacterial decomposition of crude humic acid fraction has been compared with that adsorbed by montmorillonite and illite as clay-humic acid complexes in presence of H^+ and Al^{3+} ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The bacterial decomposition has been followed according to the following scheme. In a large pyrex conical flask a thorough mixture of about 200g. of washed whitesand, humic acid sol to supply about 150 mg. of carbon, a few c. c. of a solution containing K_2HPO_4 , $MgSO_4$, a trace of $FeCl_3$, and a few drops of garden soil suspension, which supplied the necessary bacteria for decomposition, was taken. The mixture was kept just moist, care being taken to prevent any water-logging at the surface of the sand. In the case of clay-humus- Al^{3+} mixture, the medium was, however, made free of free acid (and hence possibly of Al^{3+}) before mixing with the sand and the suitable nutrients to maintain the bacterial

activity. Gradually with time humic acid decomposed; the evolved CO_2 gas was drawn out of the conical flask by a current of dry and CO_2 -free air and was absorbed in a known volume of $N/10$ - $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution. The excess of baryta was then titrated with standard oxalic acid. The process was followed at an interval of 24 hours and the amount of CO_2 evolved was expressed in terms of volume difference of $N/10$ oxalic acid between the initial reading and the reading obtained after CO_2 absorption. The same experiment under identical conditions was then performed with the clay-humic acid mixtures. In all cases the experiments were checked with a control where all but humic acid were taken. The results are recorded in Tables I to III and shown graphically in Figures 1 and 2.

TABLE I

*Bacterial decomposition of SHm.**

Amount of humic acid in 40c.c. = 0.24g.

Time (days).	Humic acid.		Blank control.	
	Vol. of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c. c. of $1.17N/10$ - $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ soln.	Diff. between successive days.	Vol. of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c. c. of $1.17 N/10$ - $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ soln.	Diff. between successive days.
0	35.1 c.c.	..	35.1 c.c.	
1	32.6	2.5 c.c.	34.2	0.90c.c.
2	33.3	1.8	34.8	0.30
3	33.6	1.5	34.8	0.30
4	34.0	1.1	34.9	0.20
6	34.1	1.0	34.95	0.15
8	34.2	0.9	35.0	0.10
10	34.5	0.6	35.1	Nil
Total		9.4 ± 0.2		1.95 ± 0.2

*SHm=Humic acid extracted from Siliguri soil.

TABLE II

*Bacterial decomposition of CI clay — SHm mixture.**

Humic acid in the mixture : clay = 1:20.

Amount of humic acid in soln. = 0.24 g.

Time (days).	Contai clay/humic acid mixture.		Contai clay/humic acid mixture in presence of Al^{3+} ion.	
	Vol of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c.c. of $1.16N/10$ - $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ soln.	Diff. between successive days.	Vol of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c.c. of $1.16N/10$ - $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ soln.	Diff. between successive days.
0	34.8 c.c.	..	34.8 c.c.	..
1	32.4	2.4 c.c.	33.0	1.8 c.c.
2	33.2	1.6	33.7	1.1
3	33.6	1.2	33.9	0.9
5	33.6	1.2	34.2	0.6
7	33.9	0.9	34.2	0.6
10	34.1	0.7	34.5	0.3
Total		8.0 ± 0.2		5.3 ± 0.2

*CI clay = Illitic clay from Contai soil.

SHm = Humic acid from Siliguri soil.

TABLE III

*Bacterial decomposition of AGM clay—SHm mixture.**

In the mixture humic acid : clay = 1 : 20.

Amount of humic acid = 0.24g.

Time (days).	Montmorillonite clay—humic acid mixture.		Montmorillonite clay—humic acid mixture in presence of Al^{3+} ion.	
	Vol. of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c.c. of $1.19N/10-Ba(OH)_2$ soln.	Difference between successive days.	Vol. of $N/10$ oxalic acid to neutralise 30 c.c. $1.19N/10-Ba(OH)_2$ soln.	Difference between successive days.
0	35.6 c.c.	..	35.6 c.c.	..
1	33.4	2.2 c.c.	34.0	1.6 c.c.
2	34.4	1.3	34.5	1.1
3	34.6	1.0	34.8	0.8
5	34.8	0.9	35.0	0.6
7	35.0	0.6	35.2	0.4
10	35.1	0.5	35.4	0.2
Total		6.5 ± 0.2		4.7 ± 0.2

*AGM=Montmorillonite clay from aquagel.

SHm=Humic acid from Siliguri soil.

FIG. 1. Bacterial decomposition of CI clay—SHm mixtures.

FIG. 2. Bacterial decomposition of AGM clay—SHm mixtures.

DISCUSSION

Humic acid can be decomposed quantitatively by strong oxidising agents like $KMnO_4$, $K_2Cr_2O_7$, or H_2O_2 in acid medium. This effect permits us to estimate the organic matter even when it remains combined with clay materials, because humic acid adsorbed on clay cannot resist oxidation by these strong oxidising agents. The bacterial oxidation, on the other hand, is a very slow process and is not so drastic. Hence in Figs. 1 and 2 the study of

the bacterial oxidation has particularly shown that the rate of decomposition of humic acid is decreased when it is mixed with clay minerals. This resistance towards oxidation is greater in case of montmorillonite-humic acid complex than illite-humic acid complex. In presence of metal ion like Al^{3+} , the decomposition of humic acid is further checked. This may be attributed to an adverse effect of Al^{3+} ions on bacterial activity. No bacterial counting was, however, done in the present experiments. It must be pointed out that the Al^{3+} content will indeed be very small under the conditions of the experiments. So it can be anticipated that clay and humic acid have been united in such a way that the easily oxidisable groups of humic acid are not available for bacterial decomposition. In other words, the humic acid has been stabilised by combining with the negative clay micelles through H^+ or metal ion bonding, the latter being stronger than the former.

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PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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